

Editorial

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The launch of a journal is always an opportunity to advance scientific knowledge, because a journal consolidates ideas and facts in a field. With this in mind, *Journal of Ecoacoustics (JEA)* aims to open a new season of theoretical, empirical and applied studies in Ecoacoustics, a recent ecological discipline that represents the development of bioacoustics studies into the ecological realm.

Sounds are important semiotic mechanisms which allow, in a very efficient way, the exchange of information between organisms and their external world. In particular, inter-individual communication and environmental perception are the two most important processes in which sounds are utilized by soniferous organisms. Ecoacoustics may be defined as the investigation of the ecological role or effect of natural and manmade sounds. Ecoacoustics is deep-rooted in biological, anthropological and cognitive domains. Under the ecoacoustic umbrella different theories, topics, methods, techniques, and applications find appropriate conceptual niches.

Recent advancements in ecoacoustics have demonstrated the capacity of this discipline to enounce important theories, to test powerful metrics of sound analysis associated with rigorous statistics, to experiment with acoustic sensors and recording digital devices, to design networks of automated acoustic monitoring, and to propose remote sensory methods for data collection in hostile and wild areas (including tropical forests, deserts, deep oceans and arctic regions).

The unprecedented human intrusion in natural systems is producing effects that sensory ecology, in particular acoustic information, can perceive prior to the ecological consequences on population dynamics and community composition becoming evident and irreversible. The anticipatory capacity of the ecoacoustics approach, due to the plasticity of acoustic display, represents an extraordinary potential for environmental monitoring, saving strategic time that can be used to adopt efficient policies of environmental protection and to plan remediation actions.

JEA intends to enhance the visibility of the ecoacoustics field, publishing perspectives, original research and reviews from terrestrial, aquatic and marine environments. The journal will be a venue for the scientific community to share opinions and data, and to develop the ecoacoustics field further.

The development of a common narrative which spans from species conservation to cultural heritage of acoustics sites, including the artistic inspiration and methods in sonic representation, are ambitious objectives that should characterize *JEA* as a “transcultural” tool, respecting the need of scientific innovation and rigor in ecology.

JEA, will publish studies that cover a broad range of topics including:

- Theory in ecoacoustics.
- Terrestrial, aquatic and marine ecoacoustic communities.
- Invertebrate and vertebrate ecoacoustics.
- Urban ecoacoustics.
- Effects of human sonic intrusion.
- Applied ecoacoustics to land management.
- Acoustic biodiversity assessment.
- Climate change and effects on ecoacoustics communities.
- Soundscape conservation and protection.
- Acoustic cultural heritage.
- Ecoacoustics and the arts.
- Ecoacoustics indices and metrics.
- Methods in passive acoustic recording and monitoring.

JEA encourages scholars to submit papers and endeavors to deliver a fast peer review, providing useful suggestions and comments to improve papers. The journal has an international editorial board that guarantees thorough and accurate reviews of submitted papers to ensure a high scientific standard for published papers.

Wherever possible *JEA* offers the opportunity to publish without charges to authors thanks to the generosity of public and private sponsors.

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Competing interests

Almo Farina declares that he has no competing interests.